

“Effect of different levels of lead & cadmium on fatty acid composition of non-polar and Polar lipids of developing mustard seeds”

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Abstract: Lead (Pb) and Cadmium (Cd) are toxic heavy metals that enter into the environment through various anthropogenic sources, and inhibit plant growth and development. Lead and Cadmium toxicity may result, disturbance in plant metabolism as a consequence of plant growth. In a pot experiment the soil application of different levels of lead and cadmium (0, 10, 20, 30, 40 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ soil) affected the lipid components (non polar and polar) of mustard seeds (*Brassica juncea*) markedly.

Keywords : Heavy Metal, Cadmium Toxicity, Lead Toxicity, Sewage sludge

1. Introduction

Pollution of environment with heavy metal such as lead, cadmium, mercury etc. directly endangers animal and human health due to their entry into the food chain (Lepp, 1981). Heavy metals are toxic for plants as well as these depress growth and yield of crops. In the past efforts have mainly been directed to examine effect of heavy metals such as lead and cadmium on plant metabolism.

Heavy metals such as lead, cadmium, mercury, arsenic and selenium are an increasing environmental problems world-wide (Zhu *et al.*, 1999). Heavy metals are toxic for plants as well as these depress growth and yield of crops. The primary toxicity mechanisms of heavy metals alter the catalytic function of enzymes, damage cellular membranes and inhibit root growth. These changes cause numerous secondary effects such as inhibition of photosynthesis, hormonal imbalance and water-stress. The toxicity symptoms seen in the presence of excessive amounts of heavy metals may be due to a range of interactions at the cellular/molecular level. Toxicity may result from binding of metals to the sulphhydryl groups in proteins, leading to an inhibition of activity or disruption of structure. Plants possess a range of potential cellular mechanisms that may be involved in the detoxification of heavy metals and thus tolerance to metal stress (Hall, 2002).

Pb is a major pollutant in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Besides natural weathering processes the main sources of Pb pollution are exhaust fumes of automobiles, chimneys of factories using Pb, effluents from the storage battery, industry, mining and smelting of Pb ores, metal plating and finishing operations, fertilizers, pesticides and additives in pigments and gasoline (Eick *et al.*, 1999). Depicts various sources, which contribute to Pb pollution in the environment. Tetraethyl and tetramethyl Pb are added to gasoline to increase the octane rating. Sewage sludge containing large quantities of Pb and other metals is regularly discharged on to field and garden soils due to increasing trends in urbanization (Paivoke, 2002). Pb-affected soils contain Pb in the range of 400-800 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ soil whereas in industrialized areas the level may reach upto 1000 $\mu\text{g Pb.g}^{-1}$ soil (Angelon and Bini, 1992). Half of the Pb-containing particulate matter falls to the ground within 100 feet of roadways and is then washed away and dispersed in the atmosphere and may be carried a considerable distance by air movements before it is eventually deposited. The accumulated Pb on the street and highways is transported to surface streams by rain water and consequently pollutes others surface waterways and soil (Laxen and Harrison, 1977). Compounds of Pb used as agricultural chemicals such as Pb arsenate, which is used as a pesticide, contaminate agricultural soils.

In contrast to the organic contaminants, which can undergo biodegradation heavy metals remain in the environment. Long-term deposition of metals in soil can lead to accumulation, transport and bio-toxicity caused by mobility and bio-availability of significant fraction of metals (Adriano *et al.*, 2004).

In recent years Lead and Cadmium have been receiving increasing attention as a potent pollutant. The possible sources of its entry into soils are through land application of sewer water and municipal sludge (Ahmad, and Abdin, 2000), aerial deposition, addition of phosphatic fertilizers and automobile emissions (Asare, and Scarisbrick, 1995 & Ashraf, and McNeilly, 2004), plants growing on Cd and Pb-supplemented or Cd and Pb-contaminated soils, aerial lead is generated mostly by combustion of gasoline in vehicles (Lagerwerff, 1967) due to fall out of large particles, road-side concentration of lead in both soil and vegetation decrease away from the traffic (Lagerwerff and Specht, 1970) and are detected upto a distance of 100 m from the road-side in vegetation. Cd & Pb enters the plant through root system, foliar absorption (Aulakh *et al.* 1980) and also by direct stem

absorption (Andrey, 2012) entering food chain and affecting the plant metabolism. The accumulation of Cd & Pb in plants may cause several physiological, biochemical and structural changes. Cadmium accumulation alters mineral nutrients uptake, inhibits stomatal opening by interacting with the water balance of plant (Hossain, *et al*, 2010), disturbs the Calvin cycle enzymes, photosynthesis, carbohydrate metabolism, changes the antioxidant metabolism (Mobin, and Khan, 2007), and lowers the crop productivity. Heavy metals cause deleterious effects on fatty acid metabolism in plants.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection and processing : The seeds of mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.) were procured from the Department of Plant Biotechnology, Hyderabad central University, Hyderabad. The chemicals and reagents used during the present investigation were of analytical grade. Mustard crop was raised in earthen pots filled with sandy loam soil in the screen house and the pots were lined with polyethylene bags to avoid contamination.

Lead and Cadmium treatment of plants: A recommended dose of nitrogen $60 \mu\text{gm g}^{-1}$ and phosphorus $30 \mu\text{gm g}^{-1}$ was given in the form of urea and potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate. The lead in the form of lead acetate and cadmium in the form of cadmium chloride is applied at the rate of 0 (control), 10, 20, 30 and $40 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ soil. After the emergence of seedlings, the number of plants were thinned to three plants per pot. Nitrogen supplied by $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ was taken in account and remaining nitrogen was supplied through urea in order to keep the level of basal dose of nitrogen equal in all the treatments. The pots were kept under natural conditions in the green house. Deionized water was used for irrigation.

Lipid Extraction: Lipids were extracted according to the method of Folch *et al.* (1957). In this method five hundred mg seed sample is crushed with 0.5 g anhydrous Sodium Sulphate and 100 ml of chloroform:methanol (2:1 v/v) solution was added. This mixture is shaken for one hour and filtered. All the extractions were pooled and solvent was distilled off under vacuum from the filtrate till lipids were completely free of the solvents. To remove water soluble impurities 20 volume of chloroform:methanol (2:1 v/v) and 5 volume of 1% NaCl solution were added. The whole contents were put in a separating funnel, shaken and allowed to stand for 5 minutes. The pure lipid fraction came in the lower chloroform layer, while soaps glycerols and other water soluble impurities remained in the upper layer. Extracted lipid separated into polar and non polar lipid fraction (Nichlos, 1964). These were then estimated gravimetrically after evaporating the solvents

Lipid Analysis: Total, polar & non polar lipids fraction were methylated by the method of Luddy *et al.* (1968). In this method, ten to fifteen mg of lipid was taken in a test tube and 0.4 ml of 0.4 N sodium methylate was added. It was covered with aluminium foil and then immersed in a water bath at 65°C to a depth of half inch and was shaken vigorously for 2-3 min. The mixture became homogenous indicating that esterification of the lipid sample was completed. The test-tube was removed and cooled to room temperature. 1 ml carbon disulphide was added and shaken for 1-2 min. Approx 100 mg of activated charcoal was also added and shaken followed by filtration. Filtrate contained all the methylated esters of fatty acids.

GC analysis: Methyl esters of fatty acids were separated in a gas chromatography (Nucon-5765), equipped with flame ionization detector. Stainless steel column ($10' \times 1/8''$) was packed with 20% diethylene glycol succinate (DEGS) on 60-80 mesh chromosorb-W. The column temperature was 190°C and the flow of the nitrogen carrier gas was maintained at $35 \text{ ml minute}^{-1}$. The peaks were identified by comparison of their retention times with those of standard fatty acids methyl esters obtained from Sigma Chemicals Company.

Statistical analysis

The area under individual peak was calculated by the formula, half the base $\times$ height and converted directly into relative percentage.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present study was carried out on mustard to investigate the effect of lead (Pb) and cadmium (Cd) on lipid metabolism during seed development. It is the comparative study of accumulation of lead and cadmium metals in *Brassica juncea* and impact on fatty acid composition of non polar and polar lipid. By this comparative study we reveal out that lead and cadmium is giving noticeable impact on fatty acid composition. The results obtained are presented in this section under the following heads:

Table 3.1 Effect of different level of lead & cadmium on fatty acid composition of non- polar lipids of developing mustard seeds.

Cd conc. ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ soil)	Fatty acid composition (%)									
	Palmitic (16:0)		Stearic (18:0)		Oleic (18:1)		Linoleic (18:2)		Linolenic (18:3)	
	Pb	Cd	Pb	Cd	Pb	Cd	Pb	Cd	Pb	Cd
Control	2.14±0.22	2.16±0.01	1.27±0.39	1.34±0.02	20.18±0.91	10.38±0.21	16.31±1.11	14.91±0.30	16.24±0.88	
10	2.06±0.32	2.35±0.02	1.84±0.26	1.16±0.01	21.62±0.89	10.65±0.15	16.30±0.96	13.51±0.40	15.18±0.66	
20	2.37±0.40	1.97±0.01	2.21±0.09	0.96±0.03	21.84±1.00	09.85±0.35	15.40±0.67	13.51±0.30	15.94±0.80	
30	2.68±0.34	2.12±0.01	2.16±0.16	1.15±0.02	22.34±1.05	10.45±0.25	12.27±0.62	13.31±0.20	16.37±0.85	
40	3.12±0.36	2.14±0.22	3.41±0.21	1.15±0.01	22.07±1.12	12.38±0.31	12.15±0.46	12.7±0.17	16.54±0.56	

Table-3.1 give results of fatty acid composition of non polar lipids show the same trend. Only there were quantitative differences in fatty acid concentrations suggesting that lead application has affected the composition considerably during development. The data in Table -3.1 depicts that palmitic acid and stearic acid increases regularly with increase in Pb concentration but in Cd treatment palmitic acid is slightly less than control. On the other hand, linoleic acid decreased continuously with a rise in Pb and Cd concentration. The linolenic acid also decreases with the seed development. The decreases in all these fatty acids may be due to increase in erucic acid. The results of effect of different levels of Lead on fatty acid composition of polar lipids of developing mustard seeds are explained in Table 3.1 which revealed that palmitic acid was lower in control as compared to Pb and Cd treatments. Within the treatments, it increased with increasing doses of lead and cadmium recording maximum at 40 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ and showing almost similar concentration at 20 and 30 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$.

3.2 Effect of different level of lead & cadmium on fatty acid composition of polar lipids of developing mustard seeds.

Pb & Cd conc. ($\mu\text{gm g}^{-1}$ soil)	Fatty acid composition (%)									
	Palmitic (16:0)		Stearic (18:0)		Oleic (18:1)		Linoleic (18:2)		Linolenic (18:3)	
	Pb	Cd	Pb	Cd	Pb	Cd	Pb	Cd	Pb	Cd
Control	12.84±0.28	9.17±0.02	2.79±0.22	1.92±0.01	29.52±0.88	25.30±0.21	29.04±1.21	25.48±0.12	17.23±0.72	18.46±0.30
10	14.26±0.65	12.74±0.02	3.03±0.26	1.27±0.02	29.84±1.10	34.35±0.35	28.13±1.03	28.50±0.30	16.64±0.68	16.25±0.25
20	14.75±0.85	13.42±0.03	5.14±0.32	1.36±0.04	31.18±1.15	32.45±0.25	28.46±1.05	28.35±0.25	16.79±0.83	16.53±0.16
30	15.38±0.56	15.04±0.28	6.18±0.36	1.55±0.02	31.09±1.14	25.45±0.26	25.18±0.99	31.25±0.25	16.18±0.63	16.45±0.25
40	14.63±0.47	15.54±0.02	6.24±0.45	1.18±0.04	31.42±1.16	28.55±0.35	24.63±1.00	28.41±0.20	16.29±0.78	14.45±0.25

This trend prevailed at all stages of development. During development, palmitic acid decreased regularly. Stearic acid was present in small amount in control but increased with increasing doses of lead and cadmium. At 40 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, it was found maximum at all the stages of development. Oleic acid on the other hand was less in control as compared to lead and cadmium treatments. At 10 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ of Pb concentration, the content of oleic acid was somewhat decreased but at 20, 30, 40 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, it increased again and found maximum at 40 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ Pb concentration. Contrary to this, the oleic acids in total and non polar lipids, were higher in control as compared to treatments and at 10 and 20 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ of Pb doses, the amount was almost same in all treatments but at 40 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, it was recorded minimum.

During seed development, the oleic acid in polar lipids increased drastically until maturity. Linoleic and Linolenic acid were higher in control as compared to Pb treatments. With increase in Pb concentration, both the fatty acids were decreased but in the case of cadmium Linoleic acid was increased and maximum at 40 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$. Same trend was observed in Linolenic acid.

4. CONCLUSION

The results of effect of different levels of lead and cadmium on fatty acid composition of non polar and polar lipids in developing mustard seeds revealed that the lipid and fatty acid composition affected by lead and cadmium doses.

Polar and non polar lipids are effected by Lead and Cadmium by nearly same But lead is more dangerous heavy metal in comparison to cadmium. Lead depress the growth and yield of crop.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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6. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors do not have any conflict of interest to declare

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